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08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
08.00.11 Marketing
08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
08.00.13 Menejment
08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

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MUNDARIJA

INNOVATSION SIYOSATNI AMALGA OSHIRISHNING USTUVOR YO'NALISHLARI – OLIY TA'LIM TRANSFORMATSIYASI, RAQAMLI MODERNIZATSIYA VA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH OMILLARI.....	13
Sharipov Kongratbay Avezimbetovich	
O'ZBEKISTON YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISHI: ZARURAT, MAQSADI VA AYRIM MUAMMOLARI, YECHIMLAR	16
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna	
FAN, TA'LIM VA ISHLAB CHIQARISHDAGI SO'NGGI TENDENSIYALAR VA INNOVATSIYALAR	25
To'ychiyev Olimjon Alijonovich	
QURILISH TASHKILOTLARIDA KREDITGA LAYOQATLILIKNI BAHOLASHNI RAQAMLASHTIRISH	30
Mavlanov Normo'min Normamatovich	
BUDJET TASHKILOTLARIDA DAVLAT XARIDLARINI SAMARALI TASHKIL ETISHDA ELEKTRON SAVDOLARNING AHAMIYATI.....	37
Turabov Sarvar Abdumalikovich	
O'ZBEKISTONNI MINTAQAVIY TA'LIM VA ILM-FAN HABIGA AYLANTIRISHNING ISTIQBOLLI YO'NALISHLARI	41
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Maxamatjon o'g'li	
HUDUDIY RIVOJLANISH STRATEGIYALARIGA INNOVATSION KOMPONENTLARNI INTEGRATSIYA QILISH USULLARI	46
Muminov Fazliddin Xusniddin o'g'li	
OROL DENGIZI MEROSI: EKOLOGIK FOJIANI BARQAROR EKOTURIZM IMKONIYATLARIGA AYLANTIRISH	52
Zufarova Nozima	
KORXONALARNING YASHIL MARKETING STRATEGIYASINI ISHLAB CHIQISH METODOLOGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	60
Ergashxodjayeva Shaxnoza Djasurovna	
O'ZBEKISTONDA ISHCHI KUCHI BOZORINING TAKRORIY AMAL QILISHINING NAZARIY JIHATLARI	66
Mamaraximov B.E.	
BANK-MOLIYA TIZIMIDA QIMMATLI QOG'OZLAR VA MOLIYAVIY INSTRUMENTLARDAN FOYDALANISH ORQALI GAROV DIVERSIFIKATSIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'LLARI.....	70
Xolbozorov Husniddin Norbek o'g'li	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA TO'QIMACHILIK SANOATIDA MARKETINGNING INNOVATSION KONSEPSIYALARI.....	76
Jumayev Olimjon Sadulloevich, Axmedova Shoxsanam Sindbod qizi	
SAVDO KORXONALARIDA EKOLOGIK MAHSULOTLARNI TARG'IB QILISH VA SOTISHNI RAG'BATLANTIRISH USULLARI	84
Jalalova Dildora Jamolovna	
DIRECTIONS OF FORMING AND PROVIDING A COMPETITIVE EXPORT-ORIENTED ECONOMY IN UZBEKISTAN	87
Asatullaev Khurshid Sunatullaevich, Nasirkhodjaeva Dilafruz Sabitkhanovna, Abdullayeva Madina Kamilovna	
FROM SCIENCE TO BUSINESS: HOW UNIVERSITIES STIMULATE INNOVATION	94
Prof. A. Bobozhonov, Prof. A.M. Shatre, Assoc. Prof. V. Kirilova Vladimirova, prof. R.Kh. Karlibaeva	
PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF GREEN TECHNOLOGIES IN UZBEKISTAN BASED ON ADVANCED INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE	100
Otamuratov Sarvar	
SPECIFIC FEATURES OF MIGRATION FROM UZBEKISTAN AND PROSPECTS FOR ORGANIZATIONAL IMPROVEMENT	105
Sabiroya Lola Shavkatovna, Shaislamova Nargiza Kabilovna	

KORXONA BARQAROR AXBOROT TIZIMINI YARATISH QIYINCHILIKLARI.....	112
Abidov Abdujabbar Abduxamidovich	
TIJORAT BANKLARI FAOLIYATIGA FOIZ RISKINING TA'SIRI VA ILMIY-NAZARIY ASOSLARI.....	119
Isakov.J.Ya	
CREATION OF A MECHANISM FOR THE DEVELOPMENT AND INTRODUCTION OF A MODEL OF COMPLETE TRANSITION TO THE NETZERO ENERGY SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN	127
Makhmudova Guljakhon N., Gulomova Nigora Farxadovna	
УСИЛЕНИЕ ВОЗДЕЙСТВИЯ ХОЗЯЙСТВЕННОГО МЕХАНИЗМА НА СТОИМОСТНУЮ ОЦЕНКУ ОСНОВНЫХ ФАКТОРОВ ПРОИЗВОДСТВА.....	133
Алишер Расулев, Сергей Воронин	
РОЛЬ ФИНАНСОВОЙ ГЛОБАЛИЗАЦИИ В РАЗВИТИИ МАЛОГО И СРЕДНЕГО ПРЕДПРИНИМАТЕЛЬСТВА: ПЕРСПЕКТИВА И ПРИКЛАДНЫЕ РЕШЕНИЯ ДЛЯ ИХ ПЕРЕХОДА К МСФО.....	143
Эргашева Шахло Тургуновна	
DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS OF AGRICULTURAL ECONOMIC ACTIVITY UNDER DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION	151
Boburjon Vafoev	
ENERGETIKA TIZIMIDAGI KORXONALAR MOLIYAVIY HOLATINING TAHLILI.....	157
Matnazar Yusupovich Raximov	
АСПЕКТЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ РАЗВИТИЕМ ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО ТУРИЗМА В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ.....	162
Очилова Хилола Фармоновна	
TA'LIM XIZMATLARI BOZORINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLAR.....	167
Abdullayev Suyun Artikovich	
THE INTERCONNECTION BETWEEN DIGITAL LEARNING PLATFORMS AND THE DIGITAL ECONOMY.....	171
Kuchkarov Takhir Safarovich, Kholmonov Shodiyor Karshiboyevich	
BANK-MOLIYA TIZIMI VA XUSUSIY SEKTORNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA YANGI TEXNOLOGIYALAR YORDAMIDA BANK FAOLIYATINI RAQAMLASHTIRISH IMKONIYATLARI	174
Norov Akmal Ruzimamatovich	
РАЗВИТИЕ БАНКОВСКО-ФИНАНСОВОЙ СИСТЕМЫ И ЧАСТНОГО СЕКТОРА В РАМКАХ ПЕРСПЕКТИВ ВСТУПЛЕНИЯ ВО ВСЕМИРНУЮ ТОРГОВУЮ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЮ	180
У.А.Юлдашева	
ЗЕЛЕННЫЕ ПОТРЕБИТЕЛИ - ПУТИ РАЗВИТИЯ ЗЕЛЕННОГО РОСТА В РАМКАХ УСТОЙЧИВОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ	185
Дехканова Наргиза Шарифовна	
ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКИЙ АУДИТ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.....	192
Ходжаева М.Х.	
TADBIRKORLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA AHOLINING MOLIYAVIY SAVODXONLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI.....	199
Akbarova Barno Shuxratovna	
SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC GROWTH THROUGH TOURISM UNDER THE GREEN ECONOMY FRAMEWORK	204
Jumayev Akbar Mahmudovich	
МАКРОИQTISODIY BARQARORLIKNI TA'MINLASHDA BANK TIZIMINI RIVOJLANTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	210
Erkinxojiyev Ismoiljon Ikromjon o'g'li	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA MINTAQAVIY SANOAT KORXONALARIDA KORPORATIV MADANIYATNI RIVOJLANTIRISH VA BOSHQARUV SAMARADORLIGINI OPTIMALLASHTIRISH.....	216
Matrizayeva Dilaram Yusupbayevna	
UZBEKISTAN AT THE CROSSROADS OF HISTORY AND GREEN INNOVATION: FROM THE GREAT SILK ROAD TO A SUSTAINABLE FUTURE	220
Avalova Gulshod Murodullayevna	

ГЛАВНЫЕ ВЕКТОРЫ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОЙ ПОЛИТИКИ ПО ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЮ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.....	226
Абдуллаева М.К.	
ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT IN THE INDUSTRIAL CLUSTERS SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN: MODERN TRENDS AND DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS.....	233
Kholikova Rukhsora Sanjarovna	
HUDUDDAGI KICHIK BIZNESNING SAMARALI TARKIBIY TUZILMASINI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA MUTASSADI TASHKILOTLARNING O'ZARO UYG'UN HARAKATINI TASHKIL ETISH.....	239
Sharipov Kuvondik Baxtiyorovich	
BUSINESS ANALYTICS IN HISTORICAL PERSPECTIVE: LESSONS FROM THE INDUSTRIAL REVOLUTION TO THE DIGITAL AGE	246
Burxonova Sabo Tulanovna	
"COST ENGINEERING"NING NAZARIY ASOSLARI VA UNI IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIKNI OSHIRISHDAGI O'RNI.....	252
Zaynitdinova Umida Djalalovna	
FEATURES AND WAYS OF FURTHER DEVELOPMENT OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY.....	256
Kobilov Alisher, Majidova Irodahon	
ПИЩЕВАЯ ИНДУСТРИЯ УЗБЕКИСТАНА: АГРАРНЫЙ ИМПУЛЬС, ЭНЕРГЕТИЧЕСКОЕ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЕ И ЦЕНОВАЯ КОНЪЮНКТУРА.....	263
Юлдашев Голибжон Тургунович, Элдорбеков Гофурбек Искандарбек угли	
INCOME INEQUALITY AND MACROECONOMIC DETERMINANTS IN UZBEKISTAN: AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS	273
Muhammad Eid Balbaa, Marina Sagatovna Abdurashidova	
РЫНОК ТРУДА В УСЛОВИЯХ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ЗЕЛЕННОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	276
Амирджанова Ситора Суннат кизи	
EKOLOGIK QO'RIQXONALARDA MONITORING JARAYONLARINING IQTISODIY VA TASHKILIY ANAMIYATI.....	282
Homidov Hamdam Hasan o'g'li	
ГАРМОНИЗАЦИЯ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ СТАНДАРТОВ БУХГАЛТЕРСКОГО УЧЕТА В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН В СООТВЕТСТВИИ С МСФО	288
Абдужалилова Дилноз Абдусаттаровна	
SUSTAINABLE TOURISM AND BIODIVERSITY PROTECTION: CASE OF UZBEKISTAN WITHIN THE UNESCO WORLD HERITAGE FRAMEWORK.....	294
Yuldasheva Dilnoza Ulugbekovna	
ПРАКТИЧЕСКОЕ ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ НЕЙРОМАРКЕТИНГА НА МАРКЕТПЛЕЙСАХ (WILDBERRIES, UZUM MARKET, ЯНДЕКС МАРКЕТ)	300
Юлдашев Жамшид Абрарович	
ЗЕЛЕНАЯ ЭКОНОМИКА КАК СТИМУЛ РАЗВИТИЯ РЫНКА ТРУДА УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	309
Шаюсупова Наргиза Тургуновна	
GLOBALLASHUV SHAROITIDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANISHI O'ZBEKISTONNING XALQARO SAVDOSIGA VA IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIGIGA TAHDID SIFATIDA.....	315
Mamatov Mamajan Ahmadjonovich	
SUG'URTA TASHKILOTLARI FAOLIYATI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH VA INNOVATSION SUG'URTA MAHSULOTLARINI JORIY QILISH MASALALARI	321
Xalikulova Gulzada Tadjimuratovna	
O'ZBEKISTON OZIQ-OVQAT BOZORIDA YASHIL MARKETING STRATEGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH ORQALI BARQAROR ISTE'MOLNI RAG'BATLANTIRISH	333
Eshmatov Sanjar Azimqulovich	
ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ЗЕЛЁНЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ В РАЗНЫХ ОТРАСЛЯХ ЭКОНОМИКИ: ГЛОБАЛЬНЫЙ ОПЫТ И НАЦИОНАЛЬНАЯ ПРАКТИКА	337
Назарова Ра'но Рустамовна, Мусаева Гавхар Ахматжон кизи	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTDA MEHNAT BOZORI: O'ZBEKISTON TAJRIBASI VA ISTIQBOLLARI.....	343
Homidjonov Fozilxon Umarxon o'g'li, Haydarov Kamoliddin Baratovich	

GREEN INVESTMENT: PATHWAYS TOWARD A SUSTAINABLE FUTURE.....	348
Odilova Sitora Sayfitdin kizi	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA O'ZBEKISTON SANOAT KORXONALARIDA MARKETING STRATEGIYALARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	351
Kutbitdinova Mohigul Inoyatovna	
QURILISH MATERIALLARI SANOATIDA YASHIL TEXNOLOGIYALAR VA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYANING BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHGA TA'SIRI	356
Metyakubov Azamat Djumanazarovich	
ELEKTR SANOAT KORXONALARINING IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA MARKETING VOSITALARIDAN FOYDALANISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	361
Tursunxo'jayev Sardor Jamoliddin o'g'li	
УЧЕТ ЗАТРАТ И МЕТОДЫ ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЯ СЕБЕСТОИМОСТИ ПРОДУКЦИИ В НЕФТЕГАЗОВОЙ ОТРАСЛИ	368
Махкамова Саида Гайратовна	
MILLIY HISOBLAR TIZIMIDA INTELLEKTUAL MULK MAHSULOTLARINI MAKROIQTISODIY DARAJADA HISOBGA OLISHNING METODOLOGIK ASOSI.....	375
Sunnatov Muxtor Ne'matovich	
RENEWABLE ENERGY AND MACROECONOMIC STABILITY IN CENTRAL ASIA: PATHWAYS WITHIN THE GREEN ECONOMY	382
Khabibullo Abdullaev	
JAHON SUG'URTA AMALIYOTI ASOSIDA O'ZBEKISTON SUG'URTA BOZORIDA YANGI RIVOJLANISH YO'NALISHLARI.....	387
Abdimovminova Saodat Taxirjonovna	
INTEGRATING DATA SCIENCE INTO GREEN FINANCING AND ECO-INNOVATIONS: ACHIEVING THE GOALS OF UZBEKISTAN-2030	397
Norboev Odil Abraevich, Kungratov Ilmurod Kuzibay ugli	
O'ZBEKISTONDA SANOAT ISHLAB CHIQRISHINI DIVERSIFIKATSIYALASH AMALIYOTI VA ISTIQBOLLARI	404
Olimov Maqsudjon Komiljon o'g'li	
СОЗДАНИЕ ЗЕЛЕННОГО ЭНЕРГЕТИЧЕСКОГО КОРИДОРА В ЕВРОПУ: РЕГИОНАЛЬНЫЙ ПОТЕНЦИАЛ АЗЕРБАЙДЖАНА, КАЗАХСТАНА И УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	411
Лала Гамидова Адиль, Арзуман Гусейнов Айдын	
MAHALLA TIZIMIDA AHOLINI OZIQ-OVQAT MAHSULOTLARIGA BO'LGAN ISTE'MOL TALABLARI MODEL.....	419
S. Qulmatova	
AHOLI ICHKI MIGRATSIYASINING MEHNAT BOZORIGA TA'SIRINI STATISTIK O'RGANISH	427
Mirolimov Mirislom Mirshokir o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTONDA BANK TIZIMINI RAQAMLASHTIRISH TENDENSIYALARI VA MUAMMOLARI	434
Jumaniyozova Mukaddas Yuldashevna	
ЗЕЛЁНЫЕ ФИНАНСЫ: ГЛОБАЛЬНЫЕ ТРЕНДЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	438
Фаттахова Муниса	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI SOHASI FAOLIYATINI DAVLAT TOMONIDAN MUVOFIQLASHTIRISH VA BOSHQARISH MEKANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	444
Tuxtamishev Shodimurod Qurbonboyevich	
MARKETING TADQIQOTLARI ASOSIDA MEVA-SABZAVOT MAHSULOTLARI EKSPORT SALONIYATINI OSHIRISH	452
Xojiyev Elshod Yoqub o'g'li	
СПОСОБЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ НАУЧНЫМИ УЧРЕЖДЕНИЯМИ В ЦЕЛЯХ ПЕРЕХОДА НА РАЗРАБОТКУ ЗЕЛЕННЫХ ИННОВАЦИЙ	459
Юдаков Александр Андреевич	
O'ZBEKISTONNI JAHON SAVDO TASHKILOTIGA A'ZO BO'LISHINING OZIQ-OVQAT XAVFSIZLIGINI TA'MINLASHGA TA'SIRI.....	466
Axmedova N.A.	

O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA KLASTERLAR FAOLIYATINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING IQTISODIY MEKANIZMI	471
<i>Sherkulov Shohruh Erkin o'g'li</i>	
DEVELOPMENT SCENARIOS OF UZBEKISTAN'S ACTIVE LABOR FORCE UNTIL 2030 AND THEIR ECONOMIC IMPLICATIONS.....	476
<i>Ganiev Bakhtiyor Zulfikor ugli, Rakhmonov Bekzod Sharibjon ugli</i>	
РАЗВИТИЕ ЗЕЛЁНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ КАК ФАКТОР СТИМУЛИРОВАНИЯ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ АКТИВНОСТИ ЖЕНЩИН В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	481
<i>Дониерова Фотимабону Алишер кизи</i>	
YASHIL ENERGETIKA VA UNING IQTISODIY TARAQQIYOTDAGI O'RNI	488
<i>Babadjanova Malika Ruzimova</i>	
BENCHMARKING IN THE AUTOMOTIVE INDUSTRY: STRATEGIES FOR SUSTAINABLE COMPETITIVENESS	492
<i>Abdurashidova Nigora</i>	
УЗБЕКИСТАН СТРЕМИТСЯ К УСТОЙЧИВОМУ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОМУ РОСТУ, ВНЕДРЯЯ ПРИНЦИПЫ «ЗЕЛЁНОЙ» ЭКОНОМИКИ	498
<i>Сагдуллаева Гулнора Ботыровна</i>	
O'ZBEKISTONDA FAOLIYAT YURITAYOTGAN KOMPANIYALARNING GLOBAL MARKETING STRATEGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH YO'NALISHLARI.....	502
<i>Sharipov Ixtiyor Baxtiyorovich</i>	
ZAIF BANDLIKDAN UNUMLI BANDLIK SARI TRANSFORMATSIYA: O'ZINI O'ZI BAND QILISH	507
<i>Qurbonov Samandar Pulatovich</i>	
ВОЗОБНОВЛЯЕМАЯ ЭНЕРГИЯ В ГЛОБАЛЬНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКЕ: ТЕКУЩИЕ ТЕНДЕНЦИИ И БУДУЩЕЕ РАЗВИТИЕ.....	514
<i>Меҳрибан Самедова Тофик</i>	
RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARNING MEHNAT UNUMDORLIGINI OSHIRISHGA TA'SIRI	521
<i>Zafar Alisherovich Mamadiev, Nodira Isametdinovna Xasanxonova</i>	
SAVDO KORXONALARIDA BUXGALTERIYA HISOBINI XALQARO STANDARTLARGA INTEGRATSIYA QILISH MEKANIZMLARI.....	526
<i>Ablazov Lazizbek Abdiquosimovich</i>	
TIJORAT BANKLARINING TRANSFORMATSIYASI JARAYONINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	530
<i>Ziyadullaev Z.</i>	
TO'LOV TIZIMI KONSEPTUAL MODELINING SHAKLLANISH TAMOYILLARI	537
<i>Toshniyozov Sherali Kamoliddinovich</i>	
STAFF PERFORMANCE EVALUATION BASED ON KPI SYSTEM INDICATORS.....	546
<i>Rakhmatullaeva Shakhnoza Khamidovna, Sadriddinova Sevinchkhon</i>	
SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT AND THE TRANSITION TO A GREEN ECONOMY IN THE CONTEXT OF GLOBAL ECONOMIC TRENDS	555
<i>Svetlana Yurievna Shatokhina</i>	
MILLIY TARBIYA OMILLARI VA MILLIY MADANIY YONDASHUV ASOSIDA TALABALARDA O'QUV TASHABBUSKORLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING NAZARIY-AMALIY ASOSLARI.....	560
<i>Azimova Nilufar Nuriddinovna</i>	
TIJORAT BANKLARI TOMONIDAN KICHIK BIZNES SUBYEKTLARINI TA'MINLASHDA BANK RESURSLARINING ROLI	567
<i>Xodjayeva Jeyrona Ravshonbek qizi</i>	
O'QUV DASTURINI INTEGRATSIYALASH VA YASHIL KO'NIKMALARNI RIVOJLANTIRISH: AKADEMIK VA SANOAT O'RTASIDAGI TAFOVUTNI YOPISSH	572
<i>Qo'ziqulova Dilfuzaxon Maxammatisaqovna</i>	
DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION AND DIGITAL PLATFORMS AS A KEY FACTOR IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL BUSINESS ENTITIES	580
<i>Rizayeva Nilufar Oblakulovna</i>	

IQTISODIY OLIY TA'LIMDA STRATEGIK INNOVATSIYALAR: YASHIL KO'NIKMALARNI MILLIY VA GLOBAL BARQARORLIK MAQSADLARI BILAN MUVOFIQLASHTIRISH	585
<i>Xasanova Zarina Maxamadaliyeva</i>	
MARKAZIY OSIYODA YASHIL IQTISODIYOT: BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH YO'LIDAGI TO'SIQLAR VA ISTIQBOLLAR.....	594
<i>Aminov Shovkat O'ktam o'g'li</i>	
ПЕСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ЗЕЛЁНЫХ ОБЛИГАЦИЙ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.....	598
<i>Саидахмедова Аида Мирзаевна</i>	
ПОВЫШЕНИЕ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ И СНИЖЕНИЕ РИСКОВ КОММЕРЧЕСКИХ БАНКОВ НА ОСНОВЕ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ ТРАНЗАКЦИЙ В ФИНАНСОВЫХ ИНФОРМАЦИОННЫХ СИСТЕМАХ С ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ СИММЕТРИЧНЫХ КРИПТОСИСТЕМ.....	605
<i>Раҳимбердиев Қ.Б.</i>	
ИНТЕГРАЦИЯ ФИНАНСОВЫХ И СТРАХОВЫХ ИНСТРУМЕНТОВ ДЛЯ СТИМУЛИРОВАНИЯ УСТОЙЧИВОГО ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РОСТА	612
<i>Ш.Ф.Кобилжонова</i>	
СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ КАПИТАЛА ХОЗЯЙСТВУЮЩИХ СУБЪЕКТОВ В КОНТЕКСТЕ РАЗВИТИЯ БАНКОВСКО-ФИНАНСОВОЙ СИСТЕМЫ И ЧАСТНОГО СЕКТОРА ЭКОНОМИКИ	618
<i>Д.А.Юлдашева</i>	
РОЛЬ БАНКОВСКО-ФИНАНСОВОЙ СИСТЕМЫ И СТРАХОВЫХ МЕХАНИЗМОВ В СТИМУЛИРОВАНИИ РАЗВИТИЯ ЧАСТНОГО СЕКТОРА	624
<i>Г.Т.Ахмедова</i>	
SUG'URTA BOZORI FAOLIYATINI RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA TRANSFORMATSIYALASH VA UNING RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISH MASALALARI.....	630
<i>Saidov Farrux Faxriddinovich</i>	
OPPORTUNITIES TO ENSURE SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC GROWTH IN THE ENERGY SECTOR THROUGH THE TRANSITION TO A GREEN ECONOMY.....	635
<i>Ulashov Aliboy Rashid ugli, Istamova Nasiba Narzillo kizi</i>	
INKLYUZIV OLIY TA'LIMDA MUSTAQIL ISHLASH JARAYONINI TASHKILLASHTIRISH.....	641
<i>Akbarova Kamola Abdujabbor qizi</i>	
YOUTH-DRIVEN PATHWAYS TO GREEN EMPLOYMENT: A THEORETICAL EXAMINATION OF INCLUSIVE ECONOMIC STRATEGIES	646
<i>Suvpulatov Ozodjon Alijon ugli</i>	
KICHIK BIZNES INFRATUZILMASINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA XORIJIY TAJRIBALAR VA UNING O'ZBEKISTON UCHUN AHAMIYATI	651
<i>Botirova Xulkar Olimjonovna</i>	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA VA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH KLASTERLARI: NAZARIY ASOSLAR VA AMALIY YONDASHUVLAR.....	655
<i>Sherkulova Nodirabegim Baxordin qizi</i>	
BIOTECHNOLOGICAL SOLUTIONS IN URBAN PLANNING: OPPORTUNITIES AND LIMITATIONS OF "LIQUID TREES"	660
<i>Nosirkulov Asadjon Ahmadjon ugli</i>	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA TIKLANADIGAN ENERGIYA MANBALARINING O'RNI.....	663
<i>Fayziyeva Dilso'z Bahodirovna</i>	
KREDIT PORTFELIDA MUAMMOLI KREDITLAR ULUSHINI KAMAYTIRISH YO'LLARI	668
<i>Salixova G.J</i>	
O'ZBEKISTONDA KANDOLAT MAHSULOTLARI BOZORINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA YASHIL MARKETING STRATEGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH.....	672
<i>Boboyorova Maftuna Xaqqul qizi, Boboyorov Islombek Xaqqul o'g'li</i>	
OLIY TA'LIM TIZIMIDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARNI QO'LLASH METODLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	675
<i>Xusniddinov Yorqinjon Muhiddin o'g'li</i>	

MODA SANOATIDA CRM TIZIMLARINI ELEKTRON SAVDO PLATFORMALARI BILAN UYG'UNLASHTIRISHDAGI TO'SIQLAR	679
Xalilova Nafisa Komilovna	
ENHANCING FOREIGN ECONOMIC RELATIONS AS A DRIVING FACTOR IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE NATIONAL ECONOMY	683
Khaitova Feruza Bahrom kizi	
MARKAZIY OSIYO MAMLAKATLARIDA XORIJIY INVESTITSIYALARNING QAYTA TIKLANUVCHI ENERGIYA MANBALARIGA TA'SIRI	687
Akishova Shaxnoza Davlet qizi	
BUXORO VILOYATIDA HUNARMANDCHILIK FAOLIYATINING RIVOJLANISH TENDENSIYALARI: TAHLIL VA ISTIQBOLLAR.....	693
Ravshanova Gulchexra Ravshanovna	
SANOATNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING MEKANIZMLARI TURLARI VA OLIMLARNING YONDASHUVLARI	698
Ne'matov Shoxruxbek Ma'murjon o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTON BANK-MOLIYA TIZIMIDA KREDIT RISKLARINI BOSHQARISH AMALIYOTINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH VA UNING XUSUSIY SEKTOR RIVOJLANISHIGA TA'SIRI.....	703
Norova Nozima Nabiyevna	
O'ZBEKISTON BANK-MOLIYA TIZIMIDA REAL SEKTORNI KREDITLASH MEKANIZMLARINI SAMARALI JORIY ETISH VA XUSUSIY SEKTOR RIVOJIGA TA'SIRI.....	709
Abduxomidov Ikromjon Maxamadin o'g'li	
MOLIYA TIZIMIDA BOJ-TARIF SIYOSATINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH VA XUSUSIY SEKTOR RIVOJLANISHIGA TA'SIRI (OZIQ-OVQAT IMPORTI MISOLIDA).....	715
Rizaev Mirmahmud Xotamjanovich	
YASHIL MARKETING VA ESG INTEGRATSIYASI: STATISTIK TAHLIL VA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI	721
Charos G'ayratova	
ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ НАПРАВЛЕНИЯ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ПРОМЫШЛЕННОГО КАПИТАЛА ДЛЯ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ УСТОЙЧИВОГО ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РОСТА В УСЛОВИЯХ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ «ЗЕЛЁНОЙ» ЭКОНОМИКИ.....	727
Г.А.Хайитбаева	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISH SHAROITIDA TIJORAT BANKLAR TOMONIDAN TADBIRKORLIK FAOLIYATINI KREDITLASH.....	734
Tajiddinov Jamshiddin Shamsutdinovich	
IQTISODIYOTNING TARKIBIY TRANSFORMATSIYASIGA XORIJIY INVESTITSIYALAR TA'SIRINI BAHOLASH MEKANIZMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	738
Shodiboyeva Dilzoda Farhodjon qizi	
MOLIYA TIZIMI BARQARORLIGI VA BUDJET TUSHUMLARINI OSHIRISHDA TASHQI IQTISODIY FAOLIYATNING AHAMIYATI.....	743
Aktamov Akbarjon Aslan o'g'li	
ENSURING SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC GROWTH IN THE TRANSITION TO A GREEN ECONOMY: AN ECONOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN CARBON EMISSIONS AND ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT.....	748
Shakhriddinova Sitara Tolibjon kizi	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISH JARAYONIDA TIJORAT BANKLARIDA INVESTITSIYA LOYIHALARI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA ESG TAMOYILLARINING ROLI	760
Ostonaqulova Gulchehraxon Muhammadyoqub qizi	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT TAMOYILLARI ASOSIDA SANOAT KORXONALARIDA YETKAZIB BERISH STRATEGIYALARINI ISHLAB CHIQISH	769
Yusupov Ulug'bek Mamayusupovich	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT KONTEKSTIDA MAKROIQTISODIY BARQARORLIKNI MUSTAHKAMLASH: XALQARO TAJRIBA VA O'ZBEKISTON AMALIYOTI.....	776
Isroilov Islomiddin Kamoliddin o'g'li	

RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA SHAROITIDA SPORT TASHKILOTLARINING YANGI BIZNES MODELLARINI ISHLAB CHIQISH	782
G'ulomov Musirmon	
O'ZBEKISTONDA IQTISODIYOTGA XORIJIY INVESTISIYALARNI JALB ETISHNING USTUVOR YO'NALISHLARI VA ISTIQBOLLARI	786
Sharipova Shahnoza Baxtiyorovna	
O'ZBEKISTONDA INVESTISIYA MUHITIGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR VA INVESTISIYALARNING IQTISODIYOTGA JALB ETILISH HOLATI TAHLILI	795
Karimova Qunduz Atanazarovna	
O'ZBEKISTON TURISTIK XIZMATLAR BOZORIDA BANDLIK TRANSFORMATSIYASINI VA UNI TARTIBGA SOLISH HOLATINI TAHLIL QILISH	804
To'xtayeva Xurshida Farxodovna	
INVESTITSIYA LOYIHALARIGA TA'SIR QILUVCHI INVESTITSIYA RISKLARINI BAHOLASH.....	811
Zohidova Ruksora Komiljon qizi	
ТИПЫ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ ФИНАНСОВЫХ РАЗВЕДОК: ОСНОВНЫЕ РАЗЛИЧИЯ, ФОРМЫ И МЕТОДЫ ОСУЩЕСТВЛЕНИЯ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ.....	817
Эсанов Шохрух Отабекович	
FACE RECOGNITION PROGRAM IN PYTHON.....	823
Khurramova Maftunakhon Zhurabekovna, Khurramov Azizjon Bakhodir ugli	
FORMATION OF ACCOUNTING POLICY FOR INTANGIBLE ASSETS.....	827
Farxod T. Abdvaxidov, Ramazon A. Abdurakhmanov	
O'ZBEKISTON EKSPORT TARKIBINI YUQORI QO'SHIMCHA QIYMATLI MAHSULOTLARGA O'TKAZISH STRATEGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	834
Raximov Eshmurod Normuradovich	
EKSPORT FAOLIYATIDA ERKIN IQTISODIY ZONALARNING SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI.....	838
Berdivaliyeva Madina Komiljon qizi	
TURIZM KLASTERLARIDA TIBBIY XIZMATLAR INTEGRATSIYASI: XALQARO TAJRIBA VA O'ZBEKISTON AMALIYOTI	841
Yazdanova Shohista Tuyg'un qizi Farxodova Shohnoza Umidbek qizi	
O'ZBEKISTON HAVO TRANSPORTI TIZIMINING JAHON IQTISODIYOTIDAGI O'RNI VA RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	850
Azimova Moxinur Nozimovna	

DIRECTIONS OF FORMING AND PROVIDING A COMPETITIVE EXPORT-ORIENTED ECONOMY IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: The theoretical and methodological foundations of the processes related to the formation of an export-oriented competitive economy and the directions of its maintenance are researched. Taking into account that the modern models of achieving competitiveness have a general character of economic development and consist of the characteristics of the formation of a competitive environment, the quality of production and its efficiency were evaluated through the method of economic modeling. Scientific potential, qualification, and scientific and technical achievements of employees in improving the system of ensuring export competitiveness; the condition of related and service sub-sectors in the main competitive sectors; demand conditions; with an emphasis on processes related to enterprise strategy and structure — scientific proposals and practical recommendations on the directions of formation and maintenance of an export-oriented competitive economy have been formulated.

Key words: export-oriented economy, globalization, country competitiveness, global competitiveness index, economic integration, competitive environment, innovative product, external business environment.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada eksportga yo'naltirilgan raqobatbardosh iqtisodiyotni shakllantirish va uni qo'llab-quvvatlash jarayonlariga oid nazariy va metodologik asoslar tadqiq etilgan. Raqobatbardoshlikka erishishning zamonaviy modellari iqtisodiy rivojlanishning umumiy xususiyatlariga ega ekanligi hamda ular raqobat muhitining shakllanishi, ishlab chiqarish sifati va samaradorligi kabi ko'rsatkichlardan iboratligi inobatga olinib, iqtisodiy modellashtirish usuli orqali baholandi. Eksport raqobatbardoshligini ta'minlash tizimini takomillashtirishda xodimlarning ilmiy salohiyati, malakasi va ilmiy-texnik yutuqlari; asosiy raqobatbardosh tarmoqlardagi tegishli va xizmat ko'rsatuvchi subsohalarning holati; talab sharoitlari; shuningdek, korxonalar strategiyasi va tuzilishiga oid jarayonlar alohida o'rganildi. Tadqiqot natijalariga asoslanib, eksportga yo'naltirilgan raqobatbardosh iqtisodiyotni shakllantirish va uni barqaror qo'llab-quvvatlash bo'yicha ilmiy taklif va amaliy tavsiyalar ishlab chiqildi.

Kalit so'zlar: eksportga yo'naltirilgan iqtisodiyot, globallashtirish, mamlakat raqobatbardoshligi, global raqobatbardoshlik indeksi, iqtisodiy integratsiya, raqobat muhiti, innovatsion mahsulot, tashqi biznes muhiti.

Аннотация: В статье исследуются теоретико-методологические основы процессов, связанных с формированием экспортно-ориентированной конкурентоспособной экономики, а также направления её поддержания. Учитывая, что современные модели достижения конкурентоспособности носят общий характер экономического развития и включают характеристики формирования конкурентной среды, качество производства и его эффективность были оценены с использованием метода экономического моделирования. Рассмотрены научный потенциал, квалификация и научно-технические достижения работников в системе обеспечения экспортной конкурентоспособности; состояние смежных и сервисных подсекторов в ключевых конкурентных отраслях;

условия спроса; а также процессы, связанные со стратегией и структурой предприятий. На основе анализа выработаны научные предложения и практические рекомендации по формированию и поддержанию экспортно-ориентированной конкурентоспособной экономики.

Ключевые слова: экспортно-ориентированная экономика, глобализация, конкурентоспособность страны, индекс глобальной конкурентоспособности, экономическая интеграция, конкурентная среда, инновационный продукт, внешняя бизнес-среда.

INTRODUCTION

In the conditions of the globalization of production and capital, the competitiveness of the national economy is of particular importance. The development of countries with an open economy in the era of globalization depends on the intensity of use of various forms of international economic relations, and each direction of international economic relations takes a special place in ensuring the country's competitiveness. At the current stage of the development of the world economy, the process of adapting to the competitive environment at the international level and ensuring competitiveness is one of the important tasks facing the economy of every country. In this regard, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoev touched on the complex directions of the urgent tasks facing the economy of our country as follows: «The open market will increase the quality of products, reduce the cost, forces to introduce new technologies, rapidly develops market reforms. To put it simply, we should be in harmony with the world production system, the requirements of the world market and the processes of economic integration» [1].

In the Global Competitiveness Index (GCI) 2020 report, the formation of cross-target development programs among countries in the formation of the long-term competitiveness index, globalization processes and Taking into account the fluctuations in various sectors of the economy in the context of the «Covid-19» pandemic it is noted that it is appropriate to define new strategies for the future directions of economic growth [2].

In the countries that introduced innovative development in the world economy, scientific research works are being carried out in areas such as high-tech medicine, robotics, artificial intelligence, modern digital communication, nanotechnologies, microchips, and electric vehicles. This, in turn, shows the coherence of science and production, and high efficiency in the field of innovation. However, important issues related to the diversity of the approach to the formation of a competitive economy in the world, the implementation of the mechanism of its introduction at different levels, and the lack of specific guidelines on this issue have not been resolved.

High rates of stable economic growth are being ensured in our country under the influence of a number of measures aimed at forming a competitive economy, increasing the influence of the domestic market in ensuring competitive advantage, improving the composition of goods and services aimed at the foreign market, and renewing the assortment. However, depending on the competitiveness of some sectors, the high level of specialization processes for the production and export of products for the world market, the priority of state regulatory processes in the manifestation of domestic economic potential, the lack of modern mechanisms of the credit and financial system, infrastructure, scientific and technical potential, incomplete formation of the parameters of target use of factors such as labor resources has a negative impact on the processes of effective use of export potential. This situation showed that it is an objective necessity to adapt the fields of science and education in the republic to the changing conditions, to «...expand and deepen internal and inter-industry cooperation relations, localize production, increase the competitiveness of industries and regions»[3]

LITERATURE REVIEW

The issues of competitiveness of the national economy and its improvement have been studied to a certain extent by foreign economists as a separate research direction. In particular, the problems of the characteristics of the formation of competitiveness on an absolute and relative basis were first discussed by A. Smith [4], D. Ricardo [5], M. Porter [6], P. Krugman [7], M. Pozner [8] have implemented a number of scientific approaches to determining the criteria and indicators describing the level of international competitiveness of the country. At the same time, a number of studies on the process of formation and development of the international level of competitiveness were conducted by G.L. Azoiev [9], R.A. Fatkhutdinov [10], and others from the CIS economists.

Research on the scientific basis of researching the conditions and factors of increasing the competitiveness of the national economy was carried out by the economists of our country Sh.D. Amirov [13], N.M. Rasulov [14], I.S. Khotamov [15], B.O. Tursunov [16] and others studied to a certain extent. However, in the scientific research carried out to date, there have been no comprehensive, specially directed independent studies dedicated to the deep research of the conditions, factors and priorities for the development of the conceptual foundations of the knowledge economy in Uzbekistan. This showed how urgent this problem is today and became the basis for conducting scientific research on this topic.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research methods such as scientific abstraction, analysis and synthesis, statistical analysis, comparative analysis, deduction, induction, forecasting, economic-mathematical research are widely used in the research work.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The GDP of the country is the only criterion based on the assessment of the competitiveness of the national economy. The influence of the leading sectors in the economy in ensuring the stability of economic growth in Uzbekistan serves to ensure high growth rates of GDP. (Table 1).

Table 1. Growth rates of the gross domestic product of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the section of economic activities in 2016-2024 (in percent) [17]

	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
GDP, total	107.5	107.1	107.3	106.9	107.2	105.9	104.4	105.4	105.7
including:									
Gross value added of networks	107.7	107.5	107.4	107.0	107.3	106.0	104.3	105.3	105.8
Net taxes on products	106.6	104.3	106.7	106.1	106.5	105.7	105.7	105.9	104.7
Gross value added of networks	107.7	107.5	107.4	107.0	107.3	106.0	104.3	105.3	105.8
Agriculture, forestry and fisheries	106.1	107.0	106.4	106.0	106.1	106.2	101.2	100.3	103.1
Industry (including construction)	105.2	107.6	109.8	107.4	108.3	105.9	105.4	111.5	108.3
industry	104.4	105.7	107.5	104.5	105.3	105.4	105.2	110.8	105.0
construction	108.1	114.5	118.4	117.6	118.8	107.2	106.0	114.3	122.9
Services	110.0	107.8	106.8	107.4	107.6	105.9	106.0	105.2	106.0
shopping, living and dining services	115.7	107.3	113.8	110.5	111.3	109.3	102.1	105.4	107.2
transportation and storage, information and communication	111.2	111.1	103.4	106.9	106.1	105.5	111.3	106.9	106.6
other service industries	107.7	106.6	106.0	106.7	107.0	104.9	105.3	104.6	105.4

It can be seen from the table that even in the complex and difficult conditions described above, high and stable rates of economic growth are maintained in the main branches and sectors of the economy. In particular, in 2024, the total production volume of industrial products increased by 6.6% compared to 2018, the production volume of agricultural products increased by 2.5%, and the volume of provided services increased by 12.5%. As a result of measures taken to stimulate domestic demand, last year's retail turnover increased by 7.9% compared to 2018. This is the result of reforms aimed at further improving and liberalizing the economy and increasing the competitiveness of products on the world market. In 2022-2026, on the basis of the action strategy for the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, deepening structural changes in the state program of the following years, increasing its competitiveness due to the modernization and diversification of the leading sectors of the national economy, funds of enterprises, credit from commercial banks, foreign investment and loans in 2024. In 2025, network programs are being implemented, which provide for 649 investment projects with a total value of 40 billion US dollars. In particular, «in 2025, 18 interstate official visits were made and agreements were reached on 1,800 projects worth 52 billion dollars. in the direction of increasing its competitiveness at the expense of modernization and diversification of the leading sectors of the national economy, 649 investment projects with a total value of 40 billion US dollars are being implemented in 2022-2026 at the expense of enterprise funds, UzTTJ, credit from commercial banks, foreign investment and loans. In particular, «in 2022, 18 interstate official visits were made and agreements were reached on 1,800 projects worth 52 billion dollars. in the direction of increasing its competitiveness at the expense of modernization and diversification of the leading sectors of the national economy, 649 investment projects with

a total value of 40 billion US dollars are being implemented in 2022-2026 at the expense of enterprise funds, UzTTJ, credit from commercial banks, foreign investment and loans. In particular, «in 2024, 18 interstate official visits were made and agreements were reached on 1,800 projects worth 52 billion dollars.

Table 2. Analysis of statistic

Years	GDP billion soums (y)	Capitalized investments billion soums (X1)	Number of economically active population (thousands) (x2)
2016	127 590.2	24 455.3	12 850.1
2017	153 311.3	30 490.1	13 163.0
2018	186,829.5	37 646.2	13 505.4
2019	221 350.9	44 810.4	13 767.7
2020	255 421.9	51 232.0	14 022.4
2021	317 476.4	72 155.2	14 357.3
2022	424 728.7	124 231.3	14 641.7
2023	529 391.4	195 927.3	14 876.4
2024	602 551.4	210 195,1	14 797.4
Total	2 818 651.7	791 132.9	125 981.4

We use the data analysis function in the EXCEL program:

Table 3. Analysis of statistic

	GDP billion soums (y)	Capitalized investments billion soums (X1)	Number of economically active population (thousands) (x2)
GDP billion soums (y)	1		
Capitalized investments billion soums (X1)	0.983588054	1	
Number of economically active population (thousands) (x2)	0.927484794	0.858123956	1

There is a direct and strong relationship between the two factors x1 and x2 that affect GDP. Because the correlation coefficient is close to 1 in both cases. $R_{yx1}=0.9835$ and $R_{yx2}=0.9274$.

Table 4. Analysis of statistic

Regression statistics	
Mnojestveniy R	0.996924259
R-squared	0.993857979
Normalized R-squared	0.992103115
Standartnaya oshibka	15401.76397
Nabludeniya	10
Dispersion analysis	
	df
Regression	2
Ostatok	7
Itogo	9
	Coefficient
Y-peresechenie	-766063.2371
Capitalized investments billion soums (X1)	1.736371531
Number of economically active population (thousands) (x2)	66.23409814

The general correlation coefficient is equal to $R_{yx1x2}=0.9969$

From this, the coefficient of determination is equal to $R^2=0.9938$. If $R^2>0.6$ is normal, it means that the factors affecting our result are reliable.

Using the table above, we write the regression equation between the outcome and the factors:

$$Y = -766063.2 + 1.7363x_1 + 66.234x_2$$

We forecast the value of GDP:

Table 5. Analysis of statistic

Years	GDP billion soums (y)	Capitalized investments billion soums (X1)	Number of economically active population (thousands) (x2)	$Y = -766063.2 + 1.7363x_1 + 66.234x_2$ Yhis=	t	t^2	t*Yhis
2016	127 590.2	24 455.3	12 850.1	127512.0608	1	1	255024,1216
2017	153 311.3	30 490.1	13 163.0	158714.9026	2	4	476144.7079
2018	186 829.5	37 646.2	13 505.4	193818.5607	3	9	775274,2426
2019	221 350.9	44 810.4	13 767.7	223630.9393	4	16	1118154,697
2020	255 421.9	51 232.0	14 022.4	251650,5632	5	25	1509903,379
2021	317 476.4	72 155.2	14 357.3	310161,282	6	36	2171128,974
2022	424 728.7	124 231.3	14 641.7	419417,964	7	49	3355343,712
2023	529 391.4	195 927.3	14 876.4	559448.9127	8	64	5035040,214
2024	602 551.4	210 195,1	14 797.4	578989.5437	9	81	5789895,437
Total	2 818 651.7	791 132.9	125 981.4	2921813.09	55	2025	20584377.85

$$\bar{Y}_t = a_0 + a_1 t,$$

we need to find this prediction equation.

For this, we calculate the following system of equations:

$$\begin{cases} a_0 n + a_1 \sum t = \sum Y \\ a_0 \sum t + a_1 \sum t^2 = \sum Y \cdot t \end{cases}$$

a_0 and $a_1 = ?$ $n=10$

$$\begin{cases} 10a_0 + 55a_1 = 2921813.09 \\ 55a_0 + 385a_1 = 20584377,85 \end{cases}$$

If we solve the system:

$$a_0 = -8779.02$$

$$a_1 = 54720.06$$

The prediction equation is:

$$Y = -8779.02 + 54720.06 \cdot t$$

$t=10+$ Forecast year-2020;

$$\text{Forecast value} = -8779.02 + 54720.06 \cdot t$$

If we forecast from 2022 to 2025:

Table 6. Analysis of statistic

Years	Forecast value = $-8779.02 + 54720.06 \cdot t$
2025	647,861.70
2026	702,581.76
2027	757 301.82
2028	812,021.88

Today, the share of manufactured and processed products in domestic and foreign markets is significant, but there is an opportunity to increase it further. This makes it urgent to pay attention to saturate the domestic market and increase the competitiveness of export-oriented products. Achieving sustainable development and increasing the competitiveness of the national economy requires having an advanced innovative economy. To achieve this, it is necessary to create equal competitive opportunities for all producers of goods in the domestic market, that is to create a favorable macroeconomic environment, to support national producers in foreign markets, and at the current stage of economic development, the state should develop a long-term competition policy based on national interests and taking into account the world situation.

In order to eliminate imbalances in the development of Uzbekistan's economy in the process of integration into the world market, the following is proposed:

Formation of state programs for the development of industrial production, taking into account the growing demand of the population for industrial products. In particular, formulating state programs for the development of sectors producing means of industrial production, ensuring the balance between them at the expense of reducing the volume of imports and increasing the volume of exports;

Harmonization of the structural composition of the annual investment program with the production process of industrial products (chemical products and products made from them, food products, etc.) that are in high demand in domestic and foreign markets.

CONCLUSION

It is necessary to take into account indicators such as the nature and speed of innovations, market capacity, the role of transaction costs in entering the market, which can stimulate domestic demand, in order to increase export competitiveness by creating a competitive environment in our country, strengthening the factor conditions affecting demand parameters. Factors such as strategic advantage of labor resources, intellectual composition of the population, level of health of the population, domestic market capacity are taken into account in determining international competitiveness. It is appropriate to take into account indicators that have a relative influence on these factors, the sources of population income, the influence of the ratio between population savings and income on investments, and the share of intellectual income of the population in GDP.

In order to ensure export competitiveness, areas such as the improvement of the tax and customs system, the liberalization of currency relations, the creation of favorable macroeconomic conditions, and the liberalization of currency relations take place as a separate research subject, while the processes of improving the market mechanism of the use of export potential in the improvement of integration processes and liberalization of foreign trade in our country have not been properly established.

In order to increase competitiveness, the first object of modernization of industrial enterprises should be content capable of meeting the demand for innovative products, compliance with state education standards, a favorable investment environment necessary for the development of innovation infrastructure, and other elements of sustainable economic growth. Increase the competitiveness of domestic goods in the foreign market based on the development of new types of products and high technologies; introduction of energy and water-saving technology, which is based on the application of new discoveries in industrial production, biotechnology, informatics and nanotechnology, and has great potential in many branches and sectors of the national economy.

In the process of developing a well-coordinated printing-training program, which provides for the full use of the potential of the country and the region, the low level of closure of the printing system, familiarizing with the results of the researches conducted in the field of foreign exchange, promising printing, and packaging in our country - high level of approach to the material and technical-technological condition. In order to deepen the integration of the national economy into the world financial and economic system, to reduce its dependence on the foreign economic market, it is necessary to diversify the export composition by increasing the share of competitive finished products in the foreign market.

Today, the process of developing an import-substituting, export-oriented strategy for the development of industrial production in the economy of our country requires the formation of current and prospective programs for improving the diversified production system.

It is recommended to ensure the formation of a national program of export development in accordance with the world market conjuncture and regional programs. In regional programs of export development. In this program:

introduction of a system of differentiated benefits in the implementation of export activities;

forming a systematic transformation of the development of the competitive environment in the sectors and sectors of the economy;

introduction of the «promotion of regional exports» strategy;
in accordance with the forecast parameters of export development, it is necessary to coordinate the system of criteria and indicators for increasing the «synergistic efficiency» of the use of production factors in the regions with the practical implementation of tasks.

In recent years, new forms and methods of decentralizing the innovation cycle are emerging in Uzbekistan. There is an intensive process of creation of new joints, the main task of which is to perform engineering and current work. An «entrepreneurial» approach to the introduction of innovations is becoming more and more widespread, in which the inventor becomes the leader of the work on the development and implementation of innovations. Increasing the competitiveness of the national economy is inextricably linked with the activation of innovative processes. Finally, a necessary condition for ensuring the competitiveness of the product is to improve the management of innovation activity and the mechanism of bringing the result of intellectual activity to the level of goods that can withstand fierce competition in the international market. Scientific-technical and scientific-production associations,

List of used literature

1. Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis on January 24, 2020. [https://buxgalter.uz/doc?id=612868_o%E2%80%98President_of_the_Republic_of_Uzbekistan_Shavkat_Mirziyoyev's_Address_to_the_High_Majlis_\(January_24,2020\)&prodid=1_vse_zakonodatelstvo_uzbekistana](https://buxgalter.uz/doc?id=612868_o%E2%80%98President_of_the_Republic_of_Uzbekistan_Shavkat_Mirziyoyev's_Address_to_the_High_Majlis_(January_24,2020)&prodid=1_vse_zakonodatelstvo_uzbekistana)
2. The Global Competitiveness Report Special Edition 2020: How Countries are Performing on the Road to Recovery. <https://www.studocu.com/row/document/helwan-university/advanced-heat-transfer/global-competitiveness-report-2020/11595531>
3. Decree No. PD-6097 dated October 29, 2020 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the concept of development of science until 2030". <https://www.lex.uz/docs/5073447>.
4. Smith A. Research on the nature and causes of the wealth of nations. – M.: Eksmo, 2016. – p. 255.
5. Ricardo D. Beginning of political economy and taxation. – M.: Eksmo, 2016. 1040-p.
6. Porter M.E. The Competitive Advantage of Nations. – Free Press; edition (June 1 1998). – 896 p.
7. Krugman P.R, Obstfeld M. International economy: Theory and politics - M.: Ekon. Fac. Mosk.gos. flour: YUNITI, 1997. 769 p.
8. M.Pozner International trade and change technology International economy. M.: TEIS, 2006. C.436.
9. Azoev G.L., Chelenkov A.P. Competitive advantages of the firm. – M.: OJSC «Typography» Novosti «, 2000. – 256 p.
10. Fatkhutdinov R.A. Competitiveness: economics, strategy, management. – M.: Infra-M, 2000. – 312 p.
11. Ergashkhodjaeva Sh.D. International competition. Study guide. -T.: TDIU, 2013.-328 p.
12. Vahabov AV, Tadjibayeva DA, Khajibakiyev Sh.Kh. World economy and international economic relations. Textbook. - T.: Baktria press, 2015.- 584 p.
13. Amirov R.A. Export of educational services as the most important factor in increasing the competitiveness and economic development of the country. Power and economy. #eight. 2018. DOI10.22394/1726139-2018-71-81.
14. Rasulov N.M., Mullabaev B.B. Strategic management of innovation processes is an important factor in increasing the competitiveness of enterprises. Scientific electronic magazine "Economy and innovative technologies". No. 5, September-October, 2014.
15. Khotamov I.S. The strategy of increasing the export potential of real sector enterprises of our country. Scientific electronic magazine "Economy and innovative technologies". No. 2 November 2011.
16. Tursunov B. «Export competitiveness: theory and practice». International Finance and Accounting 2020.3 (2020): 27.
17. www.stat.uz-The official information site of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan

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